

Managing marine resources sustainably – Ecological, societal and governance connectivity, coherence and equivalence in complex marine transboundary regions

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ABSTRACT

This overview proposes a novel typology of characteristics required to ensure that marine assessment and management is connected, coherent and/or equivalent across boundaries, both within or between national and international jurisdictions. This defines the types of connectivity, coherence nature and equivalences with their relevance and examples in a marine transboundary context. It indicates the way of identifying impediments to be addressed to ensure that the management across marine boundaries is sustainable and adequate, and it also gives examples of the way of overcoming those barriers. The typology covers natural environmental, governance (policies, politics, administration and legislation), economic and management regimes. It encompasses sector (e. g. fishing, navigation, etc.) and their activity-, pressures-, effects- and management response-footprints and Maritime Spatial Planning and Marine Protected Area-designation. This links monitoring, assessment and reporting across boundaries and within the physico-chemical and ecological realms and in marine conservation across boundaries. Finally, it shows connectivity, coherence and equivalence should reflect wider societal and cultural aspects as well as governance approaches, principles and outcomes in adjacent countries (States) and regions. These aspects are summarised by analysing the so-called 10-tenets for sustainable and successful marine management. Although this typology is developed largely from a European and North America perspective, it is proposed here for validating with examples in other areas worldwide.

1. Introduction

Most marine areas worldwide are sites of multiple human activities, from aquaculture and fisheries to oil and gas exploitation and offshore wind farms, among others (Boyes et al., 2007; United Nations, 2021; Georgian et al., 2022). Those activities occupy spatial and temporal footprints which, in turn, create footprints of their pressures, as the mechanisms creating effects, and the footprints of effects on the natural and societal systems (Elliott et al., 2020a). Those activity-, pressures- and effects-footprints then require managing in which management responses are vertically, from the local to the global, and horizontally across all the sectors (fisheries, extraction, etc.). As such, the management and planning responses and requirements also have spatial and temporal footprints (Cormier et al., 2022).

At the same time, worldwide, maritime States share national boundaries and so their activities, pressures, effects and management responses have an influence on and are influenced by developments in the adjoining State(s) (Elliott et al., 2020a); Fig. 1 indicates such a complex and dynamic situation common to most marine areas worldwide where there are activities, and hence their pressures, effects and management responses, in those transnational areas and on the high seas. Therefore, a major challenge is to ensure that managing marine resources sustainably can accommodate the similarities and differences either side of boundaries between adjacent countries (Cavallo et al., 2016, 2017), i.e. the need for transboundary connectivity, coherence and equivalence.

The major challenge in marine management is to ensure that the ecological structure and functioning are maintained and protected

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while, at the same time, ensuring that the system delivers ecosystem services from which society gains goods and benefits after inputting complementary assets and human capital (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2018; Elliott et al., 2020b; Elliott, 2023). However, within its boundary, a country may set priorities for goods and benefits that differ from the adjacent State ultimately having different demands and effects.

This paper aims to propose, define and explore the types of marine transboundary connectivity, coherence and equivalence in natural sciences, marine management, marine governance and socio-economics. The analysis identifies impediments (barriers) to achieving that connectivity, coherence and equivalence and the means of overcoming those impediments and, in particular, we focus on the methods, approaches and outcomes. At the outset, the definitions of connectivity, coherence and equivalence are proposed in Box 1.

Connectivity relates to any features that are contiguous (linked physically), not only to ecosystem abiotic and biotic components independent of State boundaries, but also to activities, pressures and effects and their footprints which may extend across State boundaries (Elliott et al., 2020a). This requires coherent policies, frameworks and processes to be implemented within and between States to ensure that management plans and programmes achieve common objectives, often within regional seas. This is important as there is no certainty that any plan and project will achieve such objectives given the scientific, management and operational uncertainties involved and the historical, cultural and societal aspirations of individual States which may be independent of the technical aspects used.

Consequently, regulatory and non-regulatory measures embedded in its legislative culture and processes (such as laws and Maritime Spatial Planning) need to be used by States to implement their plans and programmes to produce outcomes that are equivalent on either side of boundaries to address common objectives (see Cormier et al., 2022). For example, the International Maritime Organisation (IMO) codes show regulatory equivalency as recommendations that can be implemented as regulations by individual States (<https://www.imo.org/en/about/Conventions/Pages/ListOfConventions.aspx>). In this case, an individual State would implement the IMO code as a decree, law, regulations or even a guideline, all of which can be enforced differently between States.

These aspects are particularly important in environmental management blocs, such as the European Union, in which framework Directives are adopted to achieve specific outcomes within a regional sea context, even if the principle of subsidiarity allows differing implementation

between countries (e.g. for the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD; Directive 2008/56/EC, the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD; Directive, 2014/89/EU), the Water Framework Directive (WFD; Directive, 2000/60/EC)) (Boyes and Elliott, 2014; Cavallo et al., 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019; Pınarbaşı et al., 2020).

2. Connectivity, coherence or equivalence in a marine transboundary context

To create an integrated approach to marine management requires considering the physical, chemical and biological sciences and the human and societal disciplines as well as economics, engineering, management, sociology, governance, planning and human behaviour (McKinley et al., 2022). This and a large experience in marine management have enabled us to propose the typology here encompassing connectivity, coherence and equivalence within the natural sciences, marine management, socio-economic aspects and marine governance, including internationally-adopted principles (Box 2). Here, the terms boundary and transboundary are used to denote respectively an accepted line and a change between two nation states, countries or management regions.

3. Connectivity, equivalence or coherence in natural sciences

3.1. Physico-chemical connectivity

This is achieved when the water characteristics and hydrographic patterns (i.e. salinity, temperature, nutrients, currents, etc.), on both sides of the boundary, are known, linked and not distorted by human activities occurring in one or both areas across the boundary. For example, the salinity conditions and the water masses have similar characteristics on both sides of the boundary; there are physical links between them and there are no oceanographic fronts to prevent connectivity, which may create different ecoregions (Berline et al., 2014). This connectivity is prevented only by the natural hydrodynamics; for example, the Flamborough-Helgoland Front traversing the central North Sea separates the more seasonally-mixed southern area from the stratified northern area and so shows a disconnect in the physical dynamics (Ducrotoy et al., 2000). Furthermore, any human developments and structures impeding water movements, and thus the links between the physico-chemical systems, would need to be removed, to maintain a

Fig. 1. Footprints of activities in a hypothetical complex marine area and the challenge of a transnational sea – to reflect the challenges of complex marine management (MPA – Marine Protected Area, SPA – Special Protected Area, SAC – Special Area of Conservation; the mid-line between the State EEZ areas is shown in bold) (adapted from Elliott et al., 2020a).

Box 1 Definitions

Connectivity – *the state of being or being able to be connected; marine features that are linked and contiguous in some way, either naturally by ecology and hydrodynamics or by management measures (human interventions and actions); i.e. elements are joined/linked across boundaries.*

Coherence – the quality of being logical and consistent and/or the quality of being regarded as forming a whole; that there is a clear relationship between the parts, that the whole is greater than the sum of the individual parts; that there is a similarity in marine aspects in adjoining transboundary areas; that similar actions and features occur either side of a boundary; **i.e. actions are the same on each side of a boundary.**

Equivalence – that a relationship exists between two (or more) entities (e.g. national marine areas), and the relationship is described as one of likeness/sameness/similarity/equality in terms of one or more potential qualities; that the same and comparable outputs and outcomes occur either side of a boundary even if the methods used differ; **i.e. actions have the same outcome on each side of a boundary irrespective of the methods used.**

Box 2 Typology of Marine Connectivity, Coherence and Equivalence

- A. *In natural sciences* - Physico-chemical connectivity; Ecological connectivity; nature conservation coherence, equivalence and connectivity.
- B. *In socio-economy* - societal connectivity and equivalence; cultural connectivity and equivalence; economic connectivity, equivalence and coherence; sectoral connectivity, coherence and equivalence.
- C. *In marine management* - connectivity of human activity-, pressures- and effects-footprints and equivalence of management response-footprints; equivalence, connectivity and coherence of monitoring, assessment and reporting.
- D. *In marine governance* - administrative equivalence; legislative equivalence; coherence and equivalence of Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) and Marine Protected Areas (MPA)-designation; this includes equivalence of internationally-adopted principles.

good hydrophysical status, *sensu* the EU MSFD (Myrberg et al., 2019). Management actions could not overcome those impediments if it is the natural state which prevents connectivity (e.g. by a naturally-occurring hydrodynamic front). Hence, where possible and economically allowed, human developments and structures impeding water movements which distort the physico-chemical links between the systems should be removed; for example in the case of the MSFD, removal would be included in a Programme of Measures, to ensure Good Environmental Status (Börger et al., 2016).

3.2. Ecological connectivity

This refers to populations and communities either side of the boundary being connected either by their life cycles, life history, migration patterns or by the larval/seeds/spores/juvenile transport, dispersal and settlement patterns (i.e. marine functional connectivity), and that there are no interferences such as natural oceanic fronts or human activities preventing that connectivity (Darnaude et al., 2022). For example, there is genetic homogeneity and hence connectivity if a resident population of a sedentary benthic species occurs in both areas with dominant currents allowing exchange of planktonic stages within the time for metamorphosis.

In the Canadian regulatory context, protecting the functions of habitats (e.g. spawning/breeding, nursery/rearing, feeding, migration, seasonal refugia) is considered the most effective way to address priorities for conservation of species and the recovery of species at risk (DFO 2019a). However, human developments, activities and structures impeding and/or distorting water movements, and thus preventing links between the ecological systems would need to be removed or managed to mitigate the effects. Despite this, a human activity may occur only on one side of a boundary and so the connectivity cannot be restored where

possible and unless economically allowed (Bishop et al., 2017; Taormina et al., 2022). Hence, those impediments cannot be overcome by human management actions if the natural features prevent connectivity.

3.3. Nature conservation coherence, equivalence and connectivity

This coherence, equivalence and connectivity in a transboundary context relate to species and habitat conservation on each side of the boundary, that habitat units are treated equally, and that species are afforded the same protection to achieve common policy objectives for a regional sea; this is particularly important for highly mobile species and for coherent Marine Protected Area (MPA) networks (Álvarez-Romero et al., 2018). For example, that two areas have defined the same benthic habitat units, indices and indicators of habitat quality, such as there being biogenic reefs either side of the boundary which are designated as priority habitats and where priorities are set through either legislation or a management plan. This covers life cycles or life histories where one State protects a spawning ground, another one protects migration and yet another feeding areas to achieve common objectives to protect a vulnerable species or conserve a threatened species.

Other examples are ecological corridors for highly mobile species thereby ensuring linked processes, and connectivity among MPAs, ensuring dispersion, connectance, etc. (Giakoumi et al., 2019; Belote et al., 2020). This connectivity can be impeded, for example, by nature conservation management employing different practices either side of the boundary affecting the life cycle or life history of the species involved. For example, in contrast to the USA, Canada uses a regulation to protect the period of salmon migration from the marine to freshwater systems that prohibits gill-netting in those corridors (DFO 2019b).

Nature conservation connectivity is also affected by the fact that populations of highly mobile and migratory species of conservation

importance are likely to be influenced by developments away from the management areas, e.g. in breeding or nursery areas. Human activities, such as structures, can prevent biological migrations, e.g. as shown by the bird movements across offshore windfarm areas in which the birds migrate around the turbines (e.g. Wilson et al., 2010; Croll et al., 2022). As another example, different priority species and habitats occur or are so designated in the different areas and so the conservation aspects across the areas are not linked (contiguous).

Impediments occur if the priority species and habitats differ between areas although it is likely that adjoining biogeographical areas have similar habitats even if the species within them differ in name but not in biological traits. Hence, equivalence of outcomes is achieved by considering functional groups instead of named species, and major habitat types can be harmonised at a higher level of habitat hierarchy, as in the European Nature Information System (EUNIS; <https://eunis.eea.europa.eu/>). Ecological connectivity is particularly important for highly mobile species where better knowledge ensures conservation outcomes; for example, the protection of wading birds along the eastern Atlantic or western Pacific flyways, or marine mammal migration patterns (Bishop et al., 2017). Importantly, nature conservation policies in North America, the EU and the UK have an overriding aim to produce a coherent network of MPAs (DFO 2009; Lieberknecht and Jones, 2016).

4. Socio-economic connectivity, coherence and equivalence

4.1. Societal connectivity and equivalence

This refers to the interactions and involvement of the different types of stakeholders either side of a border: those undertaking potentially-damaging activities, those regulating the activities and the beneficiaries, affectees and influencers in the marine area (Newton and Elliott, 2016). Hence, societal transboundary connectivity requires that the same groups of stakeholders, or groups of different stakeholders but with the same desires and tolerances, occur either side of the boundary (are coherent even if not connected) or that these stakeholders require similar outcomes, aims and desires, based on the same principles of equity and mutual trust (hence equivalence) (Ostrom, 2009; Jay et al., 2016).

This connectivity or equivalence would not be achieved if it is difficult engaging with stakeholders either side of the boundary, that the groups of stakeholders differ or that there are no mechanisms for engaging with the wider society. Therefore, overcoming those impediments requires stakeholder engagement and conflict-resolution (Gopnik et al., 2012) and equivalence would be achieved when wide-scale dissemination of outcomes is agreed.

However, while disputes, for example in a European Union context, can be settled by the European Court of Justice (ECJ), arbitration between two member-signatories of a Regional Sea Convention is non-legally binding leaving conflict to be resolved by treaty bilateral arbitration or an individual State court. Similarly for political systems which would have to rely on bilateral agreements – transboundary disputes in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction and on the High Seas would require the intervention by the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) (Sunkin et al., 2001). Although the ECJ can arbitrate between two EU Member State signatories of an RSC, it cannot arbitrate conflicts between stakeholders on each side of the border which most often involved law suits which falls under the judiciary of individual states. Given both UN and EU treaties, one State cannot consult the citizen of another State in decision-making because it would undermine the authority of the home State of these citizens. This is well enshrined in UNCLOS and several other treaties and agreements as well as the UN Charter that guarantees sovereignty, integrity of territorial boundaries and in particular independence of political systems.

4.2. Cultural connectivity and equivalence, especially of indigenous and traditional groups

Adjoining countries are likely to have similar cultural and traditional aspects and the wishes of indigenous peoples within a country's territory are paramount, for example in the case of Australia or Canada (Belfore et al., 2006). Here, we make the distinction between the rights of indigenous people and the broader cultural values between communities (Gee et al., 2017) within the individual countries; for example, there are cultural differences between nations such as between Scotland and England in the UK but the rights of indigenous peoples such as the Sámi bridge adjacent countries in northern Scandinavia. Cultural connectivity in a transboundary context requires that any indigenous group which occurs on both sides of a boundary irrespective of the national State should have similar rights, customs and protection with regard to the use of resources, including space (i.e. custodial territory). There are few studies or assessment of culture and tradition that could impede the right of an indigenous person or any person to influence a decision e.g. Gee et al. (2017) addresses culturally significant areas in the same manner as maritime spatial planning. This is very different from natural science assessments of habitat and species that are used to inform decisions.

The same indigenous group either side of a boundary would provide connectivity whereas different indigenous groups either side would require equivalence of outcomes and even coherence of approaches. These transboundary issues would not occur if indigenous peoples either side of the boundary have incompatible values and traditions or if the rights to resources differ for indigenous peoples across the boundary. Hence, overcoming those impediments would require mediation techniques including human behavioural and cultural assessments. As such, it is imperative that traditions are respected while striving for equivalence in outcomes within the scope of their rights.

While cultural aspects of indigenous peoples are included here, this is less-common in the case of Europe although, of course, different countries can have different cultural views and values across borders. For example, Pınarbaşı et al. (2020) and Cavallo et al. (2016, 2017, 2018 and 2019) compared marine management in France and Spain, within the Bay of Biscay, and the degree of harmonisation and coherence across the international boundary; they used the term 'low-level cultural differences' between both countries as the differences in implementation of marine governance were mostly related to administrative differences.

4.3. Economic connectivity, equivalence and coherence

Economic connectivity, equivalence and coherence in a transboundary context requires that the industries and activities occurring either side of the boundary are inter-dependent (European Commission, 2022). Those managing the industries and activities need to be subject to the same constraints and practices. For example, that the same companies occur either side of the boundary (connectivity), or different companies have the same business model (coherence, equivalence) – again this is more likely for countries with similar economic systems (such as the US and Canada, countries in NW Europe, the northern Mediterranean States). Hence, this connectivity, equivalence and coherence cannot occur if there are trade barriers between the areas or barriers in obtaining permissions for carrying out activities; for example, if there are different or non-compatible environmental impact assessment and protected area regulations either side of a boundary which put a company on one side of the boundary at a disadvantage. As a precise example, any relaxation of former EU environmental protection regulations, by the UK following Brexit, would remove the 'level playing field' created by membership of the EU. Such impediments can be removed by, amongst others, the high-level removal of trade barriers and the adoption of similar and non-discriminatory Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA) and protected area assessments or arbitration through EU Treaty mechanisms or World Trade Organisation rules

regarding technical barriers to trade (WTO 1994). In the case of North America, this could be achieved through the 2020 United States-Mexico-Canada-Agreement (USMCA), the successor to NAFTA (North American Free Trade Agreement).

4.4. Sectoral connectivity, coherence and equivalence

Most sea areas have the same mixture of activities creating a complex mosaic of users and uses, as sectors, e.g. fisheries, seabed mining, navigation and shipping, offshore renewable energy, aquaculture, oil and gas extraction, etc. Hence, transboundary sectoral connectivity, coherence and equivalence requires that the corresponding sectors each side of the boundary are subject to the same constraints, management and practices; for example, fishing grounds across the boundary and where there may be straddling fish stocks, or large offshore wind farms straddling Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZ) boundaries (such as the proposed North Sea Dogger Bank windfarm where the activities, or, more likely, the pressures and effects, will straddle national boundaries).

This connectivity, equivalence and coherence may be prevented by differences between regulations for the use of the waters or seabed between adjacent areas; for example, that there are differences in quota arrangements (size, species, season limits, discard rates) for fishing or in permit systems. These impediments could be overcome by harmonising the regulations or at least their outcomes and ensuring the equivalence of industrial regulations including fisheries management. This may require conflict dispute resolution techniques (Tafon et al., 2021) leading to or requiring the harmonisation or equivalency of regulations; for example, there is already a high level of standardization in Europe through the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) and ICES (International Council for the Exploration of the Sea) control on fisheries and quota management (<https://www.ices.dk/about-ICES/who-we-are/Page/Who-we-are.aspx>). Similarly, the UNECE (UN Economic Commission for Europe, <https://unece.org/mission>) aims to normalise environmental standards and quality assurance for sectors and industries.

5. Connectivity or equivalence in marine management

5.1. Connectivity of human activity-, pressures- and effects-footprints and equivalence of management response-footprints

The footprints of particular human activities, the area covered by the pressures (as mechanisms of change emanating from the activity) and the areas showing the societal and natural effects of those pressures (changes in the natural system and impacts on human well-being and welfare) all occur across boundaries (Elliott et al., 2020a). This requires activities to be managed both singly and cumulatively, i.e. antagonistic, synergistic or additive (Lonsdale et al., 2020; Evans et al., 2021). Cumulative effects considerations and management also require national legislation and policies, for example in Canada since 2019 where the Fisheries Act and the Impact Assessment Act require that cumulative effects be considered in regulatory approvals for activities.

In this case, marine management requires that the pressures and effects occurring on one side of a boundary but emanating from activities on the other side are known and are able to be controlled (Pinarbaşı et al., 2020; Borja et al., 2022a, 2022b). For example, a windfarm on one side of a boundary impacts the water movements or seabird or cetacean populations moving to the other side or that contaminants from discharges can be moved across the boundary. Such a connectivity or equivalence requires the pressures- and effects-footprints to be known, but often scientific knowledge is not sufficient, even if the site of the activity is known and licensed (Elliott et al., 2020a; Cormier et al., 2022; Galparsoro et al., 2022); this is especially challenging if no or limited cumulative effects assessments are undertaken during permitting the activity (Lonsdale et al., 2017, 2020; Galparsoro et al., 2022). These impediments can be overcome with better knowledge of the activities in an area in relation to the local dynamics and transport of materials and

impacts and that the pressures and effects of the activities are well-known even at a generic level. This also requires similar methods for cumulative impacts assessment including an assessment of the dispersal and persistence of the pressures (Lonsdale et al., 2020).

In this context, activities and their impacts require to be identified by an EIA and regulated within the activity-footprint; an activity is usually sanctioned within a national boundary (Lonsdale et al., 2017; Cormier et al., 2022). A possible exception here is shipping where a flag-vessel from one State must comply with another State's regulations when entering its territorial waters even though these regulations are based on IMO Codes and States can implement laws and regulations relating to innocent passage under UNCLOS. The residual pressures and impacts of each activity after mitigation have footprints within the boundaries of a jurisdiction (i.e. often within State boundaries) or, more often, across one or more State jurisdictions. These pressures subsequently generate ecological or societal effects at wider scales that reflect the range of species, ecosystem processes or human uses of the sea.

The management response-footprints constitute programmes of management measures which require to be horizontally-integrated, by covering all marine sectors (fishing, transport, seabed mining, etc.), and vertically-integrated from the local to the global and vice versa (Cormier et al., 2022). Hence, while those management response-footprints under the control of a national body on one side of a boundary may differ from those of another State on the other side, at the regional and global level there should be coherence and equivalence (Gorjanc et al., 2022).

5.2. Monitoring connectivity and equivalence

Monitoring methods (of both the natural and societal features) either side of the boundary require to be the same, are intercalibrated and inter-compared, and are on the same elements producing equivalent data. Preferably, monitoring could be shared across a boundary (connectivity) but this rarely happens given that monitoring is nationally-controlled, and so there needs to be compatible outputs and the same outcomes irrespective of the methods used (equivalence). For example, that adjacent countries implementing the EU MSFD or its equivalent (such as the UK Marine Strategy (UKMS)) monitor for Good Environmental Status (Danovaro et al., 2016) use the same methods (which may be established internationally).

Such equivalence would not be achieved if one of the States does not have a comprehensive monitoring programme or its monitoring methods and standards are incompatible with providing a comparable status assessment between adjoining areas. This incompatibility can be overcome if monitoring programmes (or shared programmes) are co-ordinated, that common methods are adopted and that inter-comparison and inter-calibration exercises can harmonise the outputs and outcomes (Poikane et al., 2014).

5.3. Assessment and reporting coherence and equivalence

Following monitoring, transboundary assessment and reporting are coherent if the methods of assessment and reporting are the same either side of the boundary or equivalent if the outcomes are the same irrespective of the methods used; for example, if the same indicators, metrics and indices are used, that the same combination or weighting techniques are used and that they refer to the same or corresponding elements (e.g. piscivorous seabirds, benthic infauna, etc.) (Birk et al., 2012; European Commission, 2018; Poikane et al., 2020; Franco et al., 2021). This then should ensure that there is an equivalence of outputs and outcomes which can be collated and reported to give a complete picture of a larger sea area. For example, that the same benthic methods, indicators, reference conditions and targets and means of combining quality indicators are used either side of the boundary (e.g. Muxika et al. (2019), for the EU WFD; Franco et al. (2021) for EU MSFD and the EU Habitats Directive).

Equivalence would not be achieved if there are no suitable indicators

or there are different indicators either side of the boundary and/or that the reporting is not consistent in spatial or temporal scales or its timing. For example, Franco et al. (2021) showed that the harmonisation of monitoring, assessment and reporting is neither coherent across the various EU directives nor across countries, often with adjacent water bodies. Hence, overcoming such impediments, as with monitoring, requires coordination between the assessment and reporting based on accepted guidelines, that common methods and indices (including reference conditions and targets) are adopted and that inter-comparison and inter-calibration exercises are used as necessary to harmonise the outputs and outcomes (Gray and Elliott, 2009).

6. Connectivity, coherence or equivalence in marine governance, including internationally-adopted principles

Here governance is defined as the combination of policies, politics, administrations and legislation of an area (Fritz, 2010; Elliott et al., 2020b). Ensuring connectivity, coherence and equivalence in all elements of governance is challenging across marine areas worldwide and policies can be harmonised, for example at the global level as countries adopt the UN Sustainable Development Goals or the aims of international initiatives such as the Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainability (Borja et al., 2022a). However, the harmonisation of politics and policies is outside the present discussion given that internal political processes cannot be harmonised between States as they are protected under the UN Charter. Depending on the constitution of a State, the same applied for jurisdictional boundaries across federal, provincial or municipal entities as in the case, for example, of Canada and the United States. Therefore, emphasis is placed here on the legislation and administration equivalence and coherence.

6.1. Administrative equivalence

Maritime States sanction activities, uses and users which require managing by administrative bodies; over time those States have created a plethora of statutory bodies which can have overlapping responsibilities that often reflect the history of the political processes and ultimately legislation (e.g. Boyes and Elliott 2015). Transboundary equivalence requires comparable administrative and statutory bodies cooperating across boundaries at a higher level (e.g. Regional Seas Conventions or international convention) (Cormier et al., 2022). More usually, at a lower level (e.g. national or local government), the bodies either side need equivalences in terms of duties and procedures (Cavallo et al., 2017).

This equivalence is also achieved if there is horizontal integration of these administrative bodies with State waters to produce holistic and integrated marine management (Freire-Gibb et al., 2014). For example, in many regions globally, there is a UN Environment Programme or other Regional Sea Convention (see <https://www.unep.org/explore-topics/oceans-seas/what-we-do/regional-seas-programme>, e.g. OSPAR for the NE Atlantic) which covers both sides of the boundary. A country is likely to have bodies for Environmental Protection, Nature Conservation and activity management with duties equivalent to those comparable bodies in adjacent State waters with whom preferably it could interact.

This equivalence may be prevented if the different States have a mismatch in administrative bodies such as one not having a marine management body in favour of merging catchment, terrestrial and marine management or even one not encouraging cooperation with other bodies. Hence, such impediments can be overcome if the different administrations are mandated by their governments to cooperate and establish harmonised planning approaches (Soma et al., 2015). This requires that the different bodies agree to work together and harmonise their ways of working as well as common knowledge of the competent organisations and their competencies in level, extent and duties (Cavallo et al., 2016, 2018, 2019).

6.2. Legislative equivalence

Just as most maritime States have created complex organograms of regulatory bodies for marine management (Boyes and Elliott, 2015), they have also developed a complex framework of legislative instruments and agreements from the local to the global (Boyes and Elliott, 2014; Cormier et al., 2022). Consequently, as the State legal competence cannot extend to adjacent State areas (apart from shipping), the transboundary legislative equivalence requires the laws and agreements either side of the boundary to be compatible and equivalent (in the spirit if not in the letter of the law). This implies that the linking aspects and instruments are known on both sides of the boundary in the vertical hierarchy of laws and agreements (from the local, through national and regional to international) (Cormier et al., 2022). For example, when each State is a member of the EU and so follows EU Directives, or that each State is a signatory to a Regional Sea Convention (such as HELCOM for the Baltic, OSPAR for the NE Atlantic, etc.) (Burdon et al., 2018), and to international agreements such as the UNCLOS, IMO, Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), etc.

There may be national impediments to the implementation of each of the legislative instruments (e.g. as shown by Boyes et al. (2016), in relation to EU marine legislation) but this challenge is compounded when countries either side of a boundary differently implement such instruments. As an example, ensuring equivalence across EU borders is hampered if member States do not implement Directives in the same way (allowed under the principle of subsidiarity), or that only one is a member of the EU; for non-EU States, it may be that one or both are not signatories to international conventions or agreements although this would be unusual.

Those impediments can be overcome if each sovereign State agrees to implement national regulations that provide equivalent approaches to the management of activities and their pressures; again, for example, by fulfilling the obligations of EU Directives and regulations. This may require greater guidance in implementing the agreements and directives and possibly the need to carry out inter-comparison exercises to ensure compatibility and comparability of outcomes (e.g. HACCP (Hazard Analysis & Critical Control Points) conformity assessments for food safety or the UK NMBAQC (National Marine Biological Analytical Quality Control) Scheme for benthic analyses).

It is emphasised that whereas that compatibility and comparability may be at State level, the EU Directives do not have jurisdiction over individuals, companies or non-national organisations in an EU State and so the State would have to overcome impediments between such bodies in different States, for example by creating bilateral agreements (Soma et al., 2015). This is likely to be even more complex and problematical when implementing conservation policies in areas beyond national jurisdiction (Rochette et al., 2014).

6.3. Coherence and Equivalence of Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP)

Coherence requires that the same approaches and practices of MSP are used on both sides of the boundary or, failing that, there is an equivalence of outcomes and outputs if different approaches and practices are used (Pınarbaşı et al., 2020). This equivalence may also mean that that zoning or space allocation practices on one side of the boundary do not disadvantage groups of stakeholders on the other side of the boundary. For example, countries on both sides of the boundary would have to follow the EU MSPD and plan the use of the seabed according to agreed criteria. This equivalence may be prevented if one of the States does not practice MSP or one State allocates seabed use according to where an activity could be rather than where it should be. Those impediments may be overcome when wide-ranging MSP practices are adopted similarly by different countries or at least outcomes have equivalence (Suárez de Vivero et al., 2009). This would also be achieved if common stakeholder working groups are organized across the border (Gopnik et al., 2012) or if the objectives of MSP are common and

achieved across all countries influencing a regional sea (Cormier et al., 2016).

6.4. Marine Protected Areas (MPA)-designation coherence or equivalence

MPA-designation transboundary coherence or equivalence requires methods to be compatible or with the same outcomes, for example, with any weighting mechanisms in conservation prioritisation or that the States have similar guidelines and principles for establishing and managing MPAs, including coherence, connectivity, representativity and replication (e.g. Lieberknecht and Jones, 2016). For European countries, the MPA legislation has the main equivalence outcome of satisfying the nature conservation (Natura, 2000) Directives (EU Habitats and Wild Birds Directives).

Coherence or equivalence are not achieved if the different States use different methods, guidelines and approaches, especially for spatial and temporal delimiting, or/and that outcomes such as relating to priority species and habitats differ. Therefore, this requires transboundary coherence in the methods or at least equivalence between outcomes in MPA designation and especially a focus on dynamic (functional) rather than purely static (structural) aspects (Cashion et al., 2020). A desired outcome is that, for example, there are equivalent levels of protection for their area, such as recent European and global (UN and CBD) initiatives to protect 30% of the marine area by 2030 (<https://www.cbd.int/cop15-cbd-press-release-final-19dec2022>).

In addition to coherence between adjoining countries for MPA designation, there should be a coherent network of MPAs within a State area (Lieberknecht and Jones, 2016; Agnesi et al., 2017). As such, the designated areas should form a mosaic either with similar habitats or with populations of the same species which interact and rely on source and sink populations (i.e. larvae from one population transported to seed another population). For example, the UK network of MPAs (termed Marine Conservation Zones in English waters) was designed using agreed guidelines as an ecologically or hydrographically coherent network (Sciberras et al., 2013; Lieberknecht and Jones 2016). Similarly, European MPA are increasingly being designed as a coherent network (DELTAES, 2015).

6.5. Equivalence in internationally-adopted Principles

Transboundary considerations are increasingly important given the similarity of visions (i.e. outcomes as equivalence) adopted for territorial and EEZ waters using local, national, regional and international agreements and statutory instruments. This encompasses, all aspects from the natural to social sciences, as environmental, societal, management and governance issues. Aiming for equivalence is particularly important through internationally-adopted principles (e.g. Cormier et al., 2022; Bennett et al., 2021; Borja et al., 2022c) (Box 3), all of which

require to be embedded in transboundary marine management.

7. Towards integrated and holistic transboundary marine management

In taking the above proposals, here we emphasise that sustainable, successful, integrated and holistic marine management requires a set of ten facets to be fulfilled – the so-called 10 tenets (Elliott, 2013; Barnard and Elliott, 2015; Elliott et al., 2017). Hence, these can be cross-referenced to the proposed connectivity, coherence and equivalence typology to ensure that all aspects of marine environmental management are accommodated (Table 1). As shown by the examples given, it is suggested that these give guidance for interrogating the typology in other marine areas.

8. Concluding remarks

Most seas globally are complex and interconnected systems encompassing natural and dynamic physico-chemical and ecological features, the available administrative management and governance initiatives and embedded in societal demands and wishes. Those complex systems require a prioritisation of the issues and an overarching vision and therefore management requires analysis of the whole system (Elliott et al., 2020b). However, it is emphasised here that almost all seas straddle State borders thereby requiring transboundary science, management and governance. Therefore, achieving sustainable and successful transboundary management for adjoining maritime States within regional seas requires connectivity and coherence or, if that cannot be assured, then equivalence on both sides of a boundary.

From a planning perspective, equivalence is also required in the management of activities such as through IMO conventions and recommended Codes giving equivalency across Maritime States. Similarly, the UN Charter guarantees sovereignty and territorial integrity as well as independence for State political systems. As such, many parts of the typology here occur in instruments such as UN Charters, Conventions and EU Directives which therefore address transboundary issues. Vertical integration in transboundary governance is therefore required from the local to the global and vice versa, as shown by the management response-footprint pyramid described by Cormier et al. (2022). This is in addition to the need for the transboundary integration of horizontal governance across all sectors (Boyes and Elliott, 2014).

Transboundary cooperation in connectivity, coherence and equivalence requires marine science and management approaches which have more in common than differ between adjacent States. While this often results in a bottom-up manner from peoples in adjacent countries having similar culture, outlooks, philosophies and practices, it may also result top-down from legislative agreements and requirements based on the sea as a common resource. Most importantly, the dynamic and highly-

Box 3

Internationally-adopted Principles in Transboundary Marine Management

- sustainable development (for ecology, economy and society);
- inter-generational equity;
- environmental justice;
- the precautionary principle;
- conservation of biological diversity and ecological integrity;
- ecological and economic valuation;
- the 'damager debt'/'polluter pays' principle;
 - waste minimisation, and
 - public participation - the role of individuals (including indigenous people) and ethics.

Table 1

The 10-tenets of sustainable and successful marine management presented in the light of the characteristics of connectivity, coherence and equivalence presented in the proposed typology.

Ten-Tenet	Connectivity	Coherence	Equivalence
Socially desirable/tolerable: environmental management measures are as required or at least are understood and tolerated by society as being required; society regards the measures as necessary	Connectivity across boundaries to supply societal goods and benefits on each side of the State boundary, e.g. a pleasant seascape	There is likely to be coherence between what is desired and tolerated by the societies on both sides of the State boundary, e.g. good environmental quality	Equivalence does not apply here although it is likely that adjacent communities will desire similar outcomes in marine management
Ecologically sustainable: measures will ensure that the ecosystem features and functioning and the fundamental and final ecosystem services are safeguarded	Ecosystem components and processes extend across State boundaries, e.g. highly mobile species	Sustainability of these ecosystem features depends on the coherence of policies and their objectives, e.g. the interference in migration routes	The measures implemented within the boundaries of a State need to be equivalent to ensure sustainability of wider ecosystems, e.g. at the Regional Seas level
Economically viable: a cost–benefit assessment of the environmental management indicates (economic) viability and sustainability	Given global markets, the economic output of one State is connected to the economic outputs of other States, e.g. the loss of straddling fish stocks	Given economic interconnectedness, the viability of State economics relies on the coherence of their individual policies to ensure comparability, e.g. exploitation of seabed mineral resources	The transboundary and intraboundary measures need to be equivalent to ensure both viability and no competitive disadvantage
Technologically feasible: methods, techniques and equipment for ecosystem and society/infrastructure protection are available	Connectivity occurs if a particular industry operates on both sides of a transnational boundary using the same methods, e.g. multinational energy companies	Coherence in selecting the technologies to be implemented within both boundaries of adjacent States, e.g. the same methods of pollution control	Equivalency in the outcomes of the technologies implemented by individual States, e.g. the use of different fishing gears but with the same outcome such as bycatch limitation
Legally permissible: there are regional, national or international agreements and/or statutes which will enable and/or force the management measures to be performed	Connectivity cannot occur as sovereignty does not extend over national boundaries	Coherence between adjacent State legislation to manage activities equitably, e.g. harmonised MSFD and UKMS implementation	Equivalency of the outcomes for the inter- and intra-boundary regulations, e.g. achieving the aims of UNCLOS, IMO, SDGs and EU Directives, but using differing approaches, such as different pollution control laws
Administratively achievable: the statutory bodies such as governmental departments, environmental protection and conservation bodies are in place and functioning to enable successful and sustainable management	Connectivity is unlikely in State plans and programmes as national administrative bodies cannot operate across transnational boundaries	Coherence in the planning processes used to develop and implement plans and programmes, e.g. by similar conservation bodies with similar aims and methods such as using the same Ecological Network Guidance	Equivalency of the outcomes for the regulations implemented despite being different types of bodies, e.g. an Environmental Protection Agency in one country having the fisheries remit of a Fisheries Department in another country
Politically expedient: the management approaches and philosophies are consistent with the prevailing political climate and have the support of political leaders	Connectivity may only occur through agreements at supra-national bodies or blocs such as the EU Council of Ministers, or resolutions produced by meetings of the G7, G20, etc.	Coherence in the parliamentary processes of different States to develop similar public policies	Equivalence of political outcomes by implementing international agreements using national policies, e.g. UNCLOS, IMO, Regional Seas Agreements
Culturally inclusive: especially but not solely related to indigenous and traditional communities, local customs and practices are protected and respected	Connectivity would be achieved through related peoples traversing a transnational border, e.g. the Sámi people in northern Europe	Coherence would be achieved through similar customs, behaviour and philosophies of different cultural groups either side of a transnational border, e.g. First Nations either side of the US-Canadian NW border	Equivalence would be achieved through different cultural groups with different customs, behaviour and philosophies either side of a transnational border but producing similar outcomes
Ethically defensible (morally correct, including also justice and equity): the wishes and practices of individuals are respected in decision-making	Connectivity between peoples either side of a transnational boundary is unlikely as there would not be recognised transboundary influence	Coherence occurs through similar customs, outlooks, political philosophies and behaviour either side of a transnational border	Equivalence occurs resulting from the coherence as long as there are similar outcomes
Effectively communicable: all horizontal links and vertical hierarchies of governance are accommodated in inclusive decision-making	This is achieved through discussions and agreements on a top-down bilateral, bloc (e.g. EU), regional (e.g. RSC) and international (e.g. UN) basis, but also bottom-up by involving local communities, stakeholders and user groups. Despite effectively indicating traditional top-down communication, the range of communication types/focal areas needs to be expanded to be more inclusive of other stakeholders and local communities with a bottom-up approach		

(Acronyms: MSFD: Marine Strategy Framework Directive; UKMS: United Kingdom Marine Strategy; UNCLOS: United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea; IMO: International Maritime Organization; SDG: Sustainable Development Goals; RSC: Regional Seas Conventions.

related natural and societal features of any sea show that actions on one side of a boundary will influence features on the other side. Hence this requires cooperation and agreement whether for separate adjacent States (e.g. US and Canada), States inside a larger bloc (e.g. Spain and France), or between a State inside a bloc and one outside (e.g. between the UK and the EU Member States following Brexit). This mixture of transnational arrangements suggests that the typology proposed can be applied across adjacent maritime boundaries worldwide.

The typology proposed here and the underpinning international principles need to be embedded in marine management and governance of the States across a boundary irrespective of whether the two States are in the same bloc, e.g. both within the European Union, within a given Regional Seas Convention, or signatories to a trading bloc such as USMCA, etc. Hence, it is contended here that successful and sustainable marine management and governance cannot be achieved if there is no

equivalence in the adoption or implementation of these principles. Therefore, a wide adoption of these principles is required. In particular, there is the need for international integrated and holistic scientific monitoring, reporting and assessment which then feeds into holistic management systems (Cormier et al., 2015) for MSP across transnational boundaries and for the management of complex areas (Burdon et al., 2018).

Given that the above principles are embedded in the governance of States worldwide and in their horizontal and vertical policy integration then this is challenging but needs to be achieved. It is encouraging that to work towards achieving this, there are many recent and ongoing examples of international cooperation and collaboration coupled with bottom-up and top-down initiatives (Cormier et al., 2022), hence the ‘ocean optimism’ discussed by Borja et al. (2022a). It is finally emphasised here that this requires transboundary cooperation and

coordination within a defined framework such as the typology proposed here for interrogation across marine areas worldwide.

Declaration of competing interest

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Data availability

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